

Pathway Analysis Report

This report contains the pathway analysis results for the submitted sample ". Analysis was performed against Reactome version 85 on 24/08/2023. The web link to these results is:

<https://reactome.org/PathwayBrowser/#/ANALYSIS=MjAyMzA4MjQxODIwMTVfMjU4ODM%3D>

Please keep in mind that analysis results are temporarily stored on our server. The storage period depends on usage of the service but is at least 7 days. As a result, please note that this URL is only valid for a limited time period and it might have expired.

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1. Introduction

Reactome is a curated database of pathways and reactions in human biology. Reactions can be considered as pathway 'steps'. Reactome defines a 'reaction' as any event in biology that changes the state of a biological molecule. Binding, activation, translocation, degradation and classical biochemical events involving a catalyst are all reactions. Information in the database is authored by expert biologists, entered and maintained by Reactome's team of curators and editorial staff. Reactome content frequently cross-references other resources e.g. NCBI, Ensembl, UniProt, KEGG (Gene and Compound), ChEBI, PubMed and GO. Orthologous reactions inferred from annotation for Homo sapiens are available for 14 non-human species including mouse, rat, chicken, puffer fish, worm, fly and yeast. Pathways are represented by simple diagrams following an SBGN-like format.

Reactome's annotated data describe reactions possible if all annotated proteins and small molecules were present and active simultaneously in a cell. By overlaying an experimental dataset on these annotations, a user can perform a pathway over-representation analysis. By overlaying quantitative expression data or time series, a user can visualize the extent of change in affected pathways and its progression. A binomial test is used to calculate the probability shown for each result, and the p-values are corrected for the multiple testing (Benjamini-Hochberg procedure) that arises from evaluating the submitted list of identifiers against every pathway.

To learn more about our Pathway Analysis, please have a look at our relevant publications:

Fabregat A, Sidiropoulos K, Garapati P, Gillespie M, Hausmann K, Haw R, ... D'Eustachio P (2016). The reactome pathway knowledgebase. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 44(D1), D481–D487. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkv1351>.

Fabregat A, Sidiropoulos K, Viteri G, Forner O, Marin-Garcia P, Arnau V, ... Hermjakob H (2017). Reactome pathway analysis: a high-performance in-memory approach. *BMC Bioinformatics*, 18.

2. Properties

- This is an **overrepresentation** analysis: A statistical (hypergeometric distribution) test that determines whether certain Reactome pathways are over-represented (enriched) in the submitted data. It answers the question 'Does my list contain more proteins for pathway X than would be expected by chance?' This test produces a probability score, which is corrected for false discovery rate using the Benjamani-Hochberg method. [↗](#)
- 29 out of 29 identifiers in the sample were found in Reactome, where 768 pathways were hit by at least one of them.
- All non-human identifiers have been converted to their human equivalent. [↗](#)
- IntAct interactors were included to increase the analysis background. This greatly increases the size of Reactome pathways, which maximises the chances of matching your submitted identifiers to the expanded pathway, but will include interactors that have not undergone manual curation by Reactome and may include interactors that have no biological significance, or unexplained relevance.
- This report is filtered to show only results for species 'Homo sapiens' and resource 'all resources'.
- The unique ID for this analysis (token) is MjAyMzA4MjQxODIwMTVfMjU4ODM%3D. This ID is valid for at least 7 days in Reactome's server. Use it to access Reactome services with your data.

3. Genome-wide overview

reactome

This figure shows a genome-wide overview of the results of your pathway analysis. Reactome pathways are arranged in a hierarchy. The center of each of the circular "bursts" is the root of one top-level pathway, for example "DNA Repair". Each step away from the center represents the next level lower in the pathway hierarchy. The color code denotes over-representation of that pathway in your input dataset. Light grey signifies pathways which are not significantly over-represented.

4. Most significant pathways

The following table shows the 25 most relevant pathways sorted by p-value.

Pathway name	Entities				Reactions	
	found	ratio	p-value	FDR*	found	ratio
Cell Cycle, Mitotic	24 / 1,820	0.081	5.71e-06	0.005	90 / 352	0.025
Lagging Strand Synthesis	4 / 30	0.001	8.44e-05	0.019	4 / 11	7.69e-04
Cell Cycle	25 / 2,480	0.11	8.61e-05	0.019	109 / 451	0.032
Cell Cycle Checkpoints	9 / 540	0.024	1.17e-04	0.02	15 / 56	0.004
PCNA-Dependent Long Patch Base Excision Repair	4 / 38	0.002	1.69e-04	0.024	6 / 6	4.19e-04
G2/M Checkpoints	7 / 198	0.009	2.24e-04	0.028	11 / 24	0.002
Telomere C-strand (Lagging Strand) Synthesis	5 / 129	0.006	4.61e-04	0.045	6 / 18	0.001
Resolution of AP sites via the multiple-nucleotide patch replacement pathway	4 / 54	0.002	4.69e-04	0.045	11 / 19	0.001
Impaired BRCA2 binding to RAD51	3 / 56	0.002	5.22e-04	0.045	1 / 1	6.99e-05
Polymerase switching	2 / 16	7.11e-04	9.28e-04	0.05	3 / 4	2.80e-04
Leading Strand Synthesis	2 / 16	7.11e-04	9.28e-04	0.05	3 / 4	2.80e-04
DNA strand elongation	4 / 75	0.003	0.001	0.058	4 / 15	0.001
Defective homologous recombination repair (HRR) due to BRCA2 loss of function	3 / 82	0.004	0.002	0.07	2 / 4	2.80e-04
G1/S-Specific Transcription	6 / 182	0.008	0.002	0.071	6 / 28	0.002
Translesion synthesis by POLI	2 / 22	9.77e-04	0.002	0.071	3 / 3	2.10e-04
Translesion synthesis by POLK	2 / 23	0.001	0.002	0.074	3 / 3	2.10e-04
MHC class II antigen presentation	4 / 198	0.009	0.002	0.08	8 / 26	0.002
RHO GTPases Activate Formins	4 / 198	0.009	0.002	0.08	5 / 27	0.002
Gap-filling DNA repair synthesis and ligation in GG-NER	2 / 27	0.001	0.003	0.088	2 / 2	1.40e-04
TP53 Regulates Metabolic Genes	4 / 212	0.009	0.003	0.094	5 / 34	0.002
Regulation of TP53 Activity through Phosphorylation	4 / 221	0.01	0.003	0.105	2 / 26	0.002
Extension of Telomeres	5 / 232	0.01	0.004	0.116	6 / 28	0.002
G2/M DNA damage checkpoint	4 / 114	0.005	0.004	0.116	4 / 12	8.39e-04
Signaling by phosphorylated juxtamembrane, extracellular and kinase domain KIT mutants	2 / 35	0.002	0.004	0.116	4 / 11	7.69e-04
Removal of the Flap Intermediate from the C-strand	2 / 35	0.002	0.004	0.116	1 / 4	2.80e-04

* False Discovery Rate

5. Pathways details

For every pathway of the most significant pathways, we present its diagram, as well as a short summary, its bibliography and the list of inputs found in it.

1. Cell Cycle, Mitotic (R-HSA-69278)

The events of replication of the genome and the subsequent segregation of chromosomes into daughter cells make up the cell cycle. DNA replication is carried out during a discrete temporal period known as the S (synthesis)-phase, and chromosome segregation occurs during a massive re-organization of cellular architecture at mitosis. Two gap-phases separate these cell cycle events: G1 between mitosis and S-phase, and G2 between S-phase and mitosis. Cells can exit the cell cycle for a period and enter a quiescent state known as G0, or terminally differentiate into cells that will not divide again, but undergo morphological development to carry out the wide variety of specialized functions of individual tissues.

A family of protein serine/threonine kinases known as the cyclin-dependent kinases (CDKs) controls progression through the cell cycle. As the name suggests, the kinase activity of the catalytic subunits is dependent on binding to cyclin partners, and control of cyclin abundance is one of several mechanisms by which CDK activity is regulated throughout the cell cycle.

A complex network of regulatory processes determines whether a quiescent cell (in G0 or early G1) will leave this state and initiate the processes to replicate its chromosomal DNA and divide. This regulation, during the **Mitotic G1-G1/S phases** of the cell cycle, centers on transcriptional regulation by the DREAM complex, with major roles for D and E type cyclin proteins.

Chromosomal DNA synthesis occurs in the **S phase**, or the synthesis phase, of the cell cycle. The cell duplicates its hereditary material, and two copies of each chromosome are formed. A key aspect of the **regulation of DNA replication** is the assembly and modification of a pre-replication complex assembled on ORC proteins.

Mitotic G2-G2/M phases encompass the interval between the completion of DNA synthesis and the beginning of mitosis. During G2, the cytoplasmic content of the cell increases. At G2/M transition, duplicated centrosomes mature and separate and CDK1:cyclin B complexes become active, setting the stage for spindle assembly and chromosome condensation at the start of mitotic **M phase**. Mitosis, or M phase, results in the generation of two daughter cells each with a complete diploid set of chromosomes. Events of the **M/G1 transition**, progression out of mitosis and division of the cell into two daughters (cytokinesis) are regulated by the Anaphase Promoting Complex.

The Anaphase Promoting Complex or Cyclosome (APC/C) plays additional roles in **regulation of the mitotic cell cycle**, insuring the appropriate length of the G1 phase. The APC/C itself is regulated by phosphorylation and interactions with checkpoint proteins.

References

Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2005-01-01	Authored	Walworth N, Bosco G, O'Donnell M
2005-01-01	Created	Walworth N, Bosco G, O'Donnell M
2010-01-19	Revised	Matthews L
2011-06-15	Reviewed	Grana X
2011-08-25	Reviewed	MacPherson D
2011-08-27	Revised	Orlic-Milacic M
2013-11-25	Edited	Matthews L, Gopinathrao G
2018-07-10	Reviewed	Manfredi JJ
2023-05-21	Modified	Wright A

13 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 17 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
AURKA	O14965	CENPF	P49454	DHFR	P00374
ESCO2	Q56NI9	FEN1	P39748	GTSE1	Q9NYZ3
KIF23	Q02241	NCAPG	Q9BPX3	PKMYT1	Q99640
PPP2R5D	Q14738	RFC3	P40937, P40938	RRM2	P31350
SPC24	Q8NBT2				

Input	Ensembl Id	Input	Ensembl Id	Input	Ensembl Id
CENPF	ENSG00000117724	DHFR	ENSG00000228716	RRM2	ENSG00000171848

Interactors found in this pathway (13)

Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with	Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with
AURKA	O14965	P53350, Q9ULW0	CLTC	Q00610	Q9NYZ3
FEN1	P39748	P12004	GTSE1	Q9NYZ3	P53350
HDAC6	Q9UBN7	Q8IXJ6	PKMYT1	Q99640	P20248, P61024, P06493, P14635, O95067
PPP2R5D	Q14738	P30307	RRM2	P31350	Q9UM11
SHCBP1	Q9Z179	Q02241	STAT1	P42224	Q01094

Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with	Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with
STMN1	P16949	P46527	WRN	Q14191	P39748
XIAP	P98170	P61024			

2. Lagging Strand Synthesis (R-HSA-69186)

Cellular compartments: nucleoplasm.

Due to the antiparallel nature of DNA, DNA polymerization is unidirectional, and one strand is synthesized discontinuously. This strand is called the lagging strand. Although the polymerase switching on the lagging strand is very similar to that on the leading strand, the processive synthesis on the two strands proceeds quite differently. Short DNA fragments, about 100 bases long, called Okazaki fragments are synthesized on the RNA-DNA primers first. Strand-displacement synthesis occurs, whereby the primer-containing 5'-terminus of the adjacent Okazaki fragment is folded into a single-stranded flap structure. This flap structure is removed by endonucleases, and the adjacent Okazaki fragments are joined by DNA ligase.

References

Bambara RA, Murante RS & Henricksen LA (1997). Enzymes and reactions at the eukaryotic DNA replication fork. *J Biol Chem*, 272, 4647-50. [↗](#)

Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2023-05-21	Modified	Wright A

2 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 3 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
FEN1	P39748	RFC3	P40937, P40938

Interactors found in this pathway (1)

Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with	Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with
WRN	Q14191	P39748			

3. Cell Cycle (R-HSA-1640170)

The replication of the genome and the subsequent segregation of chromosomes into daughter cells are controlled by a series of events collectively known as the **cell cycle**. DNA replication is carried out during a discrete temporal period known as the S (synthesis)-phase, and chromosome segregation occurs during a massive reorganization to cellular architecture at mitosis. Two gap-phases separate these major cell cycle events: G1 between mitosis and S-phase, and G2 between S-phase and mitosis. In the development of the human body, cells can exit the cell cycle for a period and enter a quiescent state known as G0, or terminally differentiate into cells that will not divide again, but undergo morphological development to carry out the wide variety of specialized functions of individual tissues.

A family of protein serine/threonine kinases known as the cyclin-dependent kinases (CDKs) controls progression through the cell cycle. As the name suggests, the activity of the catalytic subunit is dependent on binding to a cyclin partner. The human genome encodes several cyclins and several CDKs, with their names largely derived from the order in which they were identified. The oscillation of cyclin abundance is one important mechanism by which these enzymes phosphorylate key substrates to promote events at the relevant time and place. Additional post-translational modifications and interactions with regulatory proteins ensure that CDK activity is precisely regulated, frequently confined to a narrow window of activity.

In addition, genome integrity in the cell cycle is maintained by the action of a number of signal transduction pathways, known as **cell cycle checkpoints**, which monitor the accuracy and completeness of DNA replication during S phase and the orderly chromosomal condensation, pairing and partition into daughter cells during mitosis.

Replication of telomeric DNA at the ends of human chromosomes and packaging of their centromeres into chromatin are two aspects of **chromosome maintenance** that are integral parts of the cell cycle.

Meiosis is the specialized form of cell division that generates haploid gametes from diploid germ cells, associated with recombination (exchange of genetic material between chromosomal homologs).

References

Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2011-10-10	Edited	Matthews L
2011-10-10	Created	Matthews L
2023-05-21	Modified	Wright A

14 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 18 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
AURKA	O14965	CENPF	P49454	DHFR	P00374
ESCO2	Q56NI9	FEN1	P39748	GTSE1	Q9NYZ3
KIF23	Q02241	NCAPG	Q9BPX3	PKMYT1	Q99640
PPP2R5D	Q14738	RFC3	P40937, P40938	RRM2	P31350
SPC24	Q8NBT2	WRN	Q14191		

Input	Ensembl Id	Input	Ensembl Id	Input	Ensembl Id
CENPF	ENSG00000117724	DHFR	ENSG00000228716	RRM2	ENSG00000171848

Interactors found in this pathway (15)

Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with	Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with
AURKA	O14965	P53350, Q9ULW0	CLTC	Q00610	Q9NYZ3
FEN1	P39748	Q14191, P54132, P12004	GTSE1	Q9NYZ3	P53350
HDAC6	Q9UBN7	Q8IXJ6	PKMYT1	Q99640	P20248, P61024, P06493, P14635, O95067
PMS1	P54277	P40692	PPP2R5D	Q14738	P30307
RFC3	P40938	P35249	RRM2	P31350	Q9UM11
SHCBP1	Q9Z179	Q02241	STAT1	P42224	Q01094
STMN1	P16949	P46527	WRN	Q14191	P54132, P39748
XIAP	P98170	P61024, P40937			

4. Cell Cycle Checkpoints (R-HSA-69620)

A hallmark of the human cell cycle in normal somatic cells is its precision. This remarkable fidelity is achieved by a number of signal transduction pathways, known as checkpoints, which monitor cell cycle progression ensuring an interdependency of S-phase and mitosis, the integrity of the genome and the fidelity of chromosome segregation.

Checkpoints are layers of control that act to delay CDK activation when defects in the division program occur. As the CDKs functioning at different points in the cell cycle are regulated by different means, the various checkpoints differ in the biochemical mechanisms by which they elicit their effect. However, all checkpoints share a common hierarchy of a sensor, signal transducers, and effectors that interact with the CDKs.

The stability of the genome in somatic cells contrasts to the almost universal genomic instability of tumor cells. There are a number of documented genetic lesions in checkpoint genes, or in cell cycle genes themselves, which result either directly in cancer or in a predisposition to certain cancer types. Indeed, restraint over cell cycle progression and failure to monitor genome integrity are likely prerequisites for the molecular evolution required for the development of a tumor. Perhaps most notable amongst these is the p53 tumor suppressor gene, which is mutated in >50% of human tumors. Thus, the importance of the checkpoint pathways to human biology is clear.

References

Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2005-01-01	Authored	Walworth N, Hoffmann I, Yen TJ, O'Donnell M, Khanna KK
2005-01-01	Created	Walworth N, Hoffmann I, Yen TJ, O'Donnell M, Khanna KK
2013-11-25	Edited	Matthews L
2023-05-19	Reviewed	Sanchez Y, Knudsen E, Hardwick KG
2023-05-21	Modified	Wright A

7 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 8 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
CENPF	P49454	GTSE1	Q9NYZ3	PKMYT1	Q99640
PPP2R5D	Q14738	RFC3	P40937, P40938	SPC24	Q8NBT2
WRN	Q14191				

Interactors found in this pathway (2)

Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with	Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with
CLTC	Q00610	Q9NYZ3	PPP2R5D	Q14738	P30307

5. PCNA-Dependent Long Patch Base Excision Repair (R-HSA-5651801)

Cellular compartments: nucleoplasm.

Long-patch base excision repair (BER) can proceed through PCNA-dependent DNA strand displacement synthesis by replicative DNA polymerases - DNA polymerase delta complex (POLD) or DNA polymerase epsilon (POLE) complex. The PCNA-dependent branch of long-patch BER may occur in cells in the S phase of the cell cycle, when the replication complexes that contain PCNA, POLD or POLE, RPA and RFC are available. POLB incorporates the first nucleotide at the 3'-end of APEX1-generated single strand break (SSB), thus displacing the damaged AP (abasic) dideoxyribose phosphate residue at the 5'-end of SSB (5'ddRP). PCNA is recruited to BER sites by APEX1 and flap endonuclease FEN1, and loaded onto damaged DNA by RFC. POLD and POLE in complex with PCNA continue the displacement DNA strand synthesis. FEN1 cleaves the displaced DNA strand with the AP residue (5'ddRP), and DNA ligase I (LIG1) ligates the multiple nucleotide patch at the 3' end of the SSB with the FEN1-processed 5'-end of the SSB (Klungland and Lindahl 1997, Stucki et al. 1998, Dianov et al. 1999, Matsumoto et al. 1999, Podlutzky et al. 2001, Dianova et al. 2001, Ranalli et al. 2002).

References

- Bohr VA, Kenny MK, Dianov GL & Jensen BR (1999). Replication protein A stimulates proliferating cell nuclear antigen-dependent repair of abasic sites in DNA by human cell extracts. *Biochemistry*, 38, 11021-5. [↗](#)
- Dogliotti E, Hübscher U, Wilson SH, Fortini P, Pascucci B, Parlanti E & Stucki M (1998). Mammalian base excision repair by DNA polymerases delta and epsilon. *Oncogene*, 17, 835-43. [↗](#)
- Podust VN, Podlutzky AJ, Dianova II, Bohr VA & Dianov GL (2001). Human DNA polymerase beta initiates DNA synthesis during long-patch repair of reduced AP sites in DNA. *EMBO J*, 20, 1477-82. [↗](#)
- Dianova II, Bohr VA & Dianov GL (2001). Interaction of human AP endonuclease 1 with flap endonuclease 1 and proliferating cell nuclear antigen involved in long-patch base excision repair. *Biochemistry*, 40, 12639-44. [↗](#)

Ranalli TA, Bambara RA & Tom S (2002). AP endonuclease 1 coordinates flap endonuclease 1 and DNA ligase I activity in long patch base excision repair. J Biol Chem, 277, 41715-24. [🔗](#)

Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2014-11-25	Created	Orlic-Milacic M
2014-12-04	Edited	Orlic-Milacic M
2014-12-04	Authored	Orlic-Milacic M
2014-12-22	Reviewed	Borowiec JA
2023-05-21	Modified	Wright A

2 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 3 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
FEN1	P39748	RFC3	P40937, P40938

Interactors found in this pathway (1)

Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with	Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with
WRN	Q14191	P39748			

6. G2/M Checkpoints (R-HSA-69481)

G2/M checkpoints include the checks for damaged DNA, unreplicated DNA, and checks that ensure that the genome is replicated once and only once per cell cycle. If cells pass these checkpoints, they follow normal transition to the M phase. However, if any of these checkpoints fail, mitotic entry is prevented by specific G2/M checkpoint events.

The G2/M checkpoints can fail due to the presence of unreplicated DNA or damaged DNA. In such instances, the cyclin-dependent kinase, Cdc2(Cdk1), is maintained in its inactive, phosphorylated state, and mitotic entry is prevented. Events that ensure that origins of DNA replication fire once and only once per cell cycle are also an example of a G2/M checkpoint.

In the event of high levels of DNA damage, the cells may also be directed to undergo apoptosis (not covered).

References

Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2003-06-05	Created	Walworth N, O'Donnell M
2023-05-21	Modified	Wright A

4 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 5 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
GTSE1	Q9NYZ3	PKMYT1	Q99640
RFC3	P40937, P40938	WRN	Q14191

Interactors found in this pathway (2)

Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with	Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with
CLTC	Q00610	Q9NYZ3	PPP2R5D	Q14738	P30307

7. Telomere C-strand (Lagging Strand) Synthesis (R-HSA-174417)

Cellular compartments: nucleoplasm.

Due to the antiparallel nature of DNA, DNA polymerization is unidirectional, and one strand is synthesized discontinuously. This strand is called the lagging strand. Although the polymerase switching on the lagging strand is very similar to that on the leading strand, the processive synthesis on the two strands proceeds quite differently. Short DNA fragments, about 100 bases long, called Okazaki fragments are synthesized on the RNA-DNA primers first. Strand-displacement synthesis occurs, whereby the primer-containing 5'-terminus of the adjacent Okazaki fragment is folded into a single-stranded flap structure. This flap structure is removed by endonucleases, and the adjacent Okazaki fragments are joined by DNA ligase.

References

Smogorzewska A & de Lange T (2004). Regulation of telomerase by telomeric proteins. *Annu Rev Biochem*, 73, 177-208. [🔗](#)

Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2006-02-17	Created	Gillespie ME
2006-03-10	Authored	Seidel J, Blackburn EH
2006-07-13	Reviewed	Price C
2009-06-03	Revised	D'Eustachio P
2020-02-12	Revised	Orlic-Milacic M
2020-04-29	Reviewed	Hayashi MT
2020-05-04	Edited	Orlic-Milacic M

Date	Action	Author
2023-05-21	Modified	Wright A

3 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 4 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
FEN1	P39748	RFC3	P40937, P40938	WRN	Q14191

Interactors found in this pathway (4)

Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with	Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with
FEN1	P39748	Q14191	RFC3	P40938	P35249
WRN	Q14191	P39748	XIAP	P98170	P40937

8. Resolution of AP sites via the multiple-nucleotide patch replacement pathway (R-HSA-110373)

Cellular compartments: nucleoplasm.

While the single nucleotide replacement pathway appears to facilitate the repair of most damaged bases, an alternative BER pathway is evoked when the structure of the 5'-terminal sugar phosphate is such that it cannot be cleaved through the AP lyase activity of DNA polymerase beta (POLB). Under these circumstances, a short stretch of residues containing the abasic site is excised and replaced (Dianov et al., 1999). Following DNA glycosylase-mediated cleavage of the damaged base, the endonuclease APEX1 is recruited to the site of damage where it cleaves the 5' side of the abasic deoxyribose residue, as in the single nucleotide replacement pathway. However, POLB then synthesizes the first replacement residue without prior cleavage of the 5'-terminal sugar phosphate, hence displacing this entity. Long-patch BER can be completed by continued POLB-mediated DNA strand displacement synthesis in the presence of PARP1 or PARP2, FEN1 and DNA ligase I (LIG1) (Prasad et al. 2001). When the PCNA-containing replication complex is available, as is the case with cells in the S-phase of the cell cycle, DNA strand displacement synthesis is catalyzed by DNA polymerase delta (POLD) or DNA polymerase epsilon (POLE) complexes, in the presence of PCNA, RPA, RFC, APEX1, FEN1 and LIG1 (Klungland and Lindahl 1997, Dianova et al. 2001). In both POLB-dependent and PCNA-dependent DNA displacement synthesis, the displaced DNA strand containing the abasic sugar phosphate creates a flap structure that is recognized and cleaved by the flap endonuclease FEN1. The replacement residues added by POLB or POLD/POLE are then ligated by the DNA ligase I (LIG1) (Klungland and Lindahl, 1997; Matsumoto et al., 1999).

References

- Bohr VA, Kenny MK, Dianov GL & Jensen BR (1999). Replication protein A stimulates proliferating cell nuclear antigen-dependent repair of abasic sites in DNA by human cell extracts. *Biochemistry*, 38, 11021-5. [↗](#)
- Lindahl T & Wood RD (1999). Quality control by DNA repair. *Science*, 286, 1897-905. [↗](#)

Dianova II, Bohr VA & Dianov GL (2001). Interaction of human AP endonuclease 1 with flap endonuclease 1 and proliferating cell nuclear antigen involved in long-patch base excision repair. *Biochemistry*, 40, 12639-44. [↗](#)

Vande Berg BJ, Wilson SH, Kim SJ, Kedar P, Yang XP, Lavrik OI & Prasad R (2001). DNA polymerase beta -mediated long patch base excision repair. Poly(ADP-ribose)polymerase-1 stimulates strand displacement DNA synthesis. *J. Biol. Chem.*, 276, 32411-4. [↗](#)

Lindhahl T & Klungland A (1997). Second pathway for completion of human DNA base excision-repair: reconstitution with purified proteins and requirement for DNase IV (FEN1). *EMBO J*, 16, 3341-8. [↗](#)

Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2004-01-29	Created	Matthews L
2004-02-03	Edited	Matthews L
2004-02-09	Authored	Matthews L
2014-12-04	Revised	Orlic-Milacic M
2014-12-04	Edited	Orlic-Milacic M
2014-12-22	Reviewed	Borowiec JA
2023-05-21	Modified	Wright A

2 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 3 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
FEN1	P39748	RFC3	P40937, P40938

Interactors found in this pathway (1)

Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with	Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with
WRN	Q14191	P39748			

9. Impaired BRCA2 binding to RAD51 (R-HSA-9709570)

Cellular compartments: nucleoplasm.

Diseases: cancer.

A critical function of BRCA2 is to bind RAD51 and nucleate RAD51 filament formation on single-stranded DNA. BRCA2 has two regions that interact with RAD51: 8 BRC repeats encoded by exon11 (Bork et al. 1996, Wong et al. 1997) and a C-terminal RAD51 binding domain called TR2 (Sharan et al. 1997).

References

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Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2020-12-11	Authored	Orlic-Milacic M
2020-12-15	Created	Orlic-Milacic M
2022-01-26	Reviewed	Le HP, Liu J, Heyer WD
2022-02-04	Edited	Orlic-Milacic M

Date	Action	Author
2023-03-08	Modified	Matthews L

2 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 3 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
RFC3	P40937, P40938	WRN	Q14191

10. Polymerase switching (R-HSA-69091)

Cellular compartments: nucleoplasm.

After the primers are synthesized, Replication Factor C binds to the 3'-end of the initiator DNA to trigger polymerase switching. The non-processive nature of pol alpha catalytic activity and the tight binding of Replication Factor C to the primer-template junction presumably lead to the turnover of the pol alpha:primase complex. After the Pol alpha-primase complex is displaced from the primer, the proliferating cell nuclear antigen (PCNA) binds to form a "sliding clamp" structure. Replication Factor C then dissociates, and DNA polymerase delta binds and catalyzes the processive synthesis of DNA.

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Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2023-05-21	Modified	Wright A

1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 2 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
RFC3	P40937, P40938

11. Leading Strand Synthesis (R-HSA-69109)

Cellular compartments: nucleoplasm.

The processive complex is responsible for synthesizing at least 5-10 kb of DNA in a continuous manner during leading strand synthesis. The incorporation of nucleotides by pol delta is quite accurate. However, incorporation of an incorrect nucleotide does occur occasionally. Misincorporated nucleotides are removed by the 3' to 5' exonucleolytic proofreading capability of pol delta.

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Date	Action	Author
2023-05-21	Modified	Wright A

1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 2 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
RFC3	P40937, P40938

Bambara RA, Murante RS & Henricksen LA (1997). Enzymes and reactions at the eukaryotic DNA replication fork. J Biol Chem, 272, 4647-50. [↗](#)

Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2003-06-05	Authored	Tom S, Bambara RA
2003-06-05	Created	Tom S, Bambara RA
2023-05-21	Modified	Wright A

2 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 3 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
FEN1	P39748	RFC3	P40937, P40938

Interactors found in this pathway (1)

Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with	Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with
WRN	Q14191	P39748			

13. Defective homologous recombination repair (HRR) due to BRCA2 loss of function (R-HSA-9701190)

Cellular compartments: nucleoplasm.

Diseases: cancer.

BRCA2 (FANCD1) is a tumor suppressor gene located on chromosomal arm 13q. BRCA2 protein is a mediator of the core mechanism of homologous recombination repair (HRR), essential for the recruitment of RAD51 recombinase to resected DNA double-strand breaks (DSBs). Monoallelic pathogenic germline mutations in BRCA2 are one of the underlying causes of the hereditary breast and ovarian cancer (HBOC) syndrome, with carriers having close to 50% lifetime risk for development of breast cancer and about 15% lifetime risk for development of ovarian cancer. In addition, BRCA2 germline mutation carriers are predisposed to cancers of the fallopian tube, pancreas, stomach, larynx and prostate. Biallelic germline mutations in BRCA2 cause Fanconi anemia subtype characterized by brain and soft tissue tumors, including medulloblastoma and Wilms tumor. BRCA2-deficient cells are defective in the formation of RAD51 foci upon treatment with DSB-inducing DNA damaging agents and accumulate chromatid breaks and radial chromosomes.

Besides its crucial role in HRR, BRCA2 is also implicated in protection of replication forks, centrosome duplication, spindle assembly checkpoint and cytokinesis. Recently published studies show the involvement of BRCA2 in the turnover of R-loops (hybrids between RNA and single strand DNA that are generated as intermediates of gene transcription). Unscheduled accumulated R-loops may be processed into DSBs, leading to genomic instability. Finally, BRCA2 is involved in pathway choice of DSB repair by inhibiting DNA polymerase theta-mediated end-joining (TMEJ) until M-phase (reviewed in Petropoulos and Halazonetis 2021, and Llorens-Agost et al. 2021). TMEJ is the predominant pathway for microhomology-mediated end joining MMEJ/alternative-nonhomologous end joining (alt-NHEJ, a-EJ) in mammals (reviewed in Ramsden et al. 2022).

BRCA2 haploinsufficiency is frequently observed in cancers, with close to 50% of BRCA2-mutant breast cancers retaining one wild type allele, suggesting that in some tissues at least heterozygous loss of BRCA2 function is sufficient for carcinogenesis. Promoter hypermethylation is not an obvious contributor to BRCA2 gene inactivation and no pathogenic mutations in the promoter region have been identified so far.

For review, please refer to Roy et al. 2011, Nalepa and Clapp 2018, Santana dos Santos et al. 2018, Venkitaraman 2019, Le et al. 2021, and Llorens-Agost et al. 2021.

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Date	Action	Author
2020-09-24	Created	Orlic-Milacic M
2020-12-11	Authored	Orlic-Milacic M
2022-01-26	Reviewed	Le HP, Liu J, Heyer WD
2022-02-04	Edited	Orlic-Milacic M
2023-03-08	Modified	Matthews L

2 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 3 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
RFC3	P40937, P40938	WRN	Q14191

14. G1/S-Specific Transcription (R-HSA-69205)

Cellular compartments: nucleoplasm.

The E2F family of transcription factors regulate the transition from the G1 to the S phase in the cell cycle. E2F activity is regulated by members of the retinoblastoma protein (pRb) family, resulting in the tight control of the expression of E2F-responsive genes. Phosphorylation of pRb by cyclin D:CDK complexes releases pRb from E2F, inducing E2F-targeted genes such as cyclin E.

E2F1 binds to E2F binding sites on the genome activating the synthesis of the target proteins. For annotation purposes, the reactions regulated by E2F1 are grouped under this pathway and information about the target genes alone are displayed for annotation purposes.

Cellular targets for activation by E2F1 include thymidylate synthase (TYMS) (DeGregori et al. 1995), Rir2 (RRM2) (DeGregori et al. 1995, Giangrande et al. 2004), Dihydrofolate reductase (DHFR) (DeGregori et al. 1995, Wells et al. 1997, Darbinian et al. 1999), Cdc2 (CDK1) (Furukawa et al. 1994, DeGregori et al. 1995, Zhu et al. 2004), Cyclin A1 (CCNA1) (DeGregori et al. 1995, Liu et al. 1998), CDC6 (DeGregori et al. 1995, Yan et al. 1998; Ohtani et al. 1998), CDT1 (Yoshida and Inoue 2004), CDC45 (Arata et al. 2000), Cyclin E (CCNE1) (Ohtani et al. 1995), Emi1 (FBXO5) (Hsu et al. 2002), and ORC1 (Ohtani et al. 1996, Ohtani et al. 1998). The activation of TK1 (Dnk1) (Dou et al. 1994, DeGregori et al. 1995, Giangrande et al. 2004) and CDC25A (DeGregori et al. 1995, Vigo et al. 1999) by E2F1 is conserved in *Drosophila* (Duronio and O'Farrell 1994, Reis and Edgar 2004).

RRM2 protein is involved in dNTP level regulation and activation of this enzyme results in higher levels of dNTPs in anticipation of S phase. E2F activation of RRM2 has been shown also in *Drosophila* by Duronio and O'Farrell (1994). E2F1 activation of CDC45 is shown in mouse cells by using human E2F1 construct (Arata et al. 2000). Cyclin E is also transcriptionally regulated by E2F1. Cyclin E protein plays important role in the transition of G1 in S phase by associating with CDK2 (Ohtani et al. 1996). E2F1-mediated activation of PCNA has been demonstrated in *Drosophila* (Duronio and O'Farrell 1994) and in some human cells by using recombinant adenovirus constructs (DeGregori et al. 1995). E2F1-mediated activation of the DNA polymerase alpha subunit p180 (POLA1) has been demonstrated in some human cells. It has also been demonstrated in *Drosophila* by Ohtani and Nevins (1994). It has been observed in *Drosophila* that E2F1 induced expression of Orc1 stimulates ORC1 6 complex formation and binding to the origin of replication (Asano and Wharton 1999). ORC1 6 recruit CDC6 and CDT1 that are required to recruit the MCM2 7 replication helicases. E2F1 regulation incorporates a feedback mechanism wherein Geminin (GMNN) can inhibit MCM2 7 recruitment of ORC1 6 complex by interacting with CDC6/CDT1. The activation of CDC25A and TK1 (Dnk1) by E2F1 has been inferred from similar events in *Drosophila* (Duronio RJ and O'Farrell 1994; Reis and Edgar 2004). E2F1 activates string (CDC25) that in turn activates the complex of Cyclin B and CDK1. A similar phenomenon has been observed in mouse NIH 3T3 cells and in Rat1 cells.

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Date	Action	Author
2003-06-05	Created	Walworth N, O'Donnell M
2023-03-08	Modified	Matthews L

2 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 4 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
DHFR	P00374	RRM2	P31350

Input	Ensembl Id
DHFR	ENSG00000228716

Input	Ensembl Id
RRM2	ENSG00000171848

Interactors found in this pathway (2)

Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with
FEN1	P39748	P12004

Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with
PKMYT1	Q99640	P06493

Murakumo Y, Akagi J, Kanjo N, Hanaoka F, Ohmori H, Ohashi E & Masutani C (2004). Interaction of hREV1 with three human Y-family DNA polymerases. *Genes Cells*, 9, 523-31. [↗](#)

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Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2014-12-10	Created	Orlic-Milacic M
2014-12-11	Edited	Orlic-Milacic M
2014-12-11	Authored	Orlic-Milacic M
2015-01-07	Reviewed	Borowiec JA
2023-05-30	Modified	Wright A

1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 2 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
RFC3	P40937, P40938

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Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2014-12-09	Created	Orlic-Milacic M
2014-12-11	Edited	Orlic-Milacic M
2014-12-11	Authored	Orlic-Milacic M
2015-01-07	Reviewed	Borowiec JA
2023-05-30	Modified	Wright A

1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 2 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
RFC3	P40937, P40938

17. MHC class II antigen presentation (R-HSA-2132295)

Antigen presenting cells (APCs) such as B cells, dendritic cells (DCs) and monocytes/macrophages express major histocompatibility complex class II molecules (MHC II) at their surface and present exogenous antigenic peptides to CD4⁺ T helper cells. CD4⁺ T cells play a central role in immune protection. On their activation they stimulate differentiation of B cells into antibody-producing B-cell blasts and initiate adaptive immune responses. MHC class II molecules are transmembrane glycoprotein heterodimers of alpha and beta subunits. Newly synthesized MHC II molecules present in the endoplasmic reticulum bind to a chaperone protein called invariant (Ii) chain. The binding of Ii prevents the premature binding of self antigens to the nascent MHC molecules in the ER and also guides MHC molecules to endocytic compartments. In the acidic endosomal environment, Ii is degraded in a stepwise manner, ultimately to free the class II peptide-binding groove for loading of antigenic peptides. Exogenous antigens are internalized by the APC by receptor mediated endocytosis, phagocytosis or pinocytosis into endocytic compartments of MHC class II positive cells, where engulfed antigens are degraded in a low pH environment by multiple acidic proteases, generating MHC class II epitopes. Antigenic peptides are then loaded into the class II ligand-binding groove. The resulting class II peptide complexes then move to the cell surface, where they are scanned by CD4⁺ T cells for specific recognition (Berger & Roche 2009, Zhou & Blum 2004, Watts 2004, Landsverk et al. 2009).

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Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2012-02-21	Edited	Garapati P V
2012-02-21	Authored	Garapati P V
2012-02-21	Created	Garapati P V
2012-05-14	Reviewed	Neeffes J
2023-05-21	Modified	Wright A

3 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 4 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
CLTC	Q00610, Q00610-1	KIF23	Q02241	KIF4A	O95239

18. RHO GTPases Activate Formins (R-HSA-5663220)

Cellular compartments: cytosol, nucleoplasm, plasma membrane, endosome membrane.

Formins are a family of proteins with 15 members in mammals, organized into 8 subfamilies. Formins are involved in the regulation of actin cytoskeleton. Many but not all formin family members are activated by RHO GTPases. Formins that serve as effectors of RHO GTPases belong to different formin subfamilies but they all share a structural similarity to *Drosophila* protein diaphanous and are hence named diaphanous-related formins (DRFs).

DRFs activated by RHO GTPases contain a GTPase binding domain (GBD) at their N-terminus, followed by formin homology domains 3, 1, and 2 (FH3, FH1, FH2) and a diaphanous autoregulatory domain (DAD) at the C-terminus. Most DRFs contain a dimerization domain (DD) and a coiled-coil region (CC) in between FH3 and FH1 domains (reviewed by Kuhn and Geyer 2014). RHO GTPase-activated DRFs are autoinhibited through the interaction between FH3 and DAD which is disrupted upon binding to an active RHO GTPase (Li and Higgs 2003, Lammers et al. 2005, Nezami et al. 2006). Since formins dimerize, it is not clear whether the FH3-DAD interaction is intra- or intermolecular. FH2 domain is responsible for binding to the F-actin and contributes to the formation of head-to-tail formin dimers (Xu et al. 2004). The proline-rich FH1 domain interacts with the actin-binding proteins profilins, thereby facilitating actin recruitment to formins and accelerating actin polymerization (Romero et al. 2004, Kovar et al. 2006).

Different formins are activated by different RHO GTPases in different cell contexts. FMNL1 (formin-like protein 1) is activated by binding to the RAC1:GTP and is involved in the formation of lamellipodia in macrophages (Yayoshi-Yamamoto et al. 2000) and is involved in the regulation of the Golgi complex structure (Colon-Franco et al. 2011). Activation of FMNL1 by CDC42:GTP contributes to the formation of the phagocytic cup (Seth et al. 2006). Activation of FMNL2 (formin-like protein 2) and FMNL3 (formin-like protein 3) by RHOC:GTP is involved in cancer cell motility and invasiveness (Kitzing et al. 2010, Vega et al. 2011). DIAPH1, activated by RHOA:GTP, promotes elongation of actin filaments and activation of SRF-mediated transcription which is inhibited by unpolymerized actin (Miralles et al. 2003). RHOF-mediated activation of DIAPH1 is implicated in formation of stress fibers (Fan et al. 2010). Activation of DIAPH1 and DIAPH3 by RHOB:GTP leads to actin coat formation around endosomes and regulates endosome motility and trafficking (Fernandez-Borja et al. 2005, Wallar et al. 2007). Endosome trafficking is also regulated by DIAPH2 transcription isoform 3 (DIAPH2-3) which, upon activation by RHOD:GTP, recruits SRC kinase to endosomes (Tomimaga et al. 2000, Gasman et al. 2003). DIAPH2 transcription isoform 2 (DIAPH2-2) is involved in mitosis where, upon being activated by CDC42:GTP, it facilitates the capture of astral microtubules by kinetochores (Yasuda et al. 2004, Cheng et al. 2011). DIAPH2 is implicated in ovarian maintenance and premature ovarian failure (Bione et al. 1998). DAAM1, activated by RHOA:GTP, is involved in linking WNT signaling to cytoskeleton reorganization (Habas et al. 2001).

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Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2014-10-24	Authored	Orlic-Milacic M
2014-12-26	Authored	Rivero Crespo F
2015-01-17	Created	Orlic-Milacic M
2015-02-02	Edited	Orlic-Milacic M
2023-05-21	Modified	Wright A

4 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 4 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
CENPF	P49454
PPP2R5D	Q14738

Input	UniProt Id
DVL3	Q92997
SPC24	Q8NBT2

19. Gap-filling DNA repair synthesis and ligation in GG-NER (R-HSA-5696397)

Cellular compartments: nucleoplasm.

Global genome nucleotide excision repair (GG-NER) is completed by DNA repair synthesis that fills the single stranded gap created after dual incision of the damaged DNA strand and excision of the ~27-30 bases long oligonucleotide that contains the lesion. DNA synthesis is performed by DNA polymerases epsilon or delta, or the Y family DNA polymerase kappa (POLK), which are loaded to the repair site after 5' incision (Staresincic et al. 2009, Ogi et al. 2010). DNA ligases LIG1 or LIG3 (as part of the LIG3:XRCC1 complex) ligate the newly synthesized stretch of oligonucleotides to the incised DNA strand (Moser et al. 2007).

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Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2004-01-29	Authored	Hoeijmakers JH
2004-02-02	Authored	Gopinathrao G
2015-05-28	Created	Orlic-Milacic M
2015-06-16	Revised	Orlic-Milacic M
2015-06-16	Edited	Orlic-Milacic M

Date	Action	Author
2015-06-16	Authored	Orlic-Milacic M
2015-08-03	Reviewed	Foster M
2023-05-30	Modified	Wright A

1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 2 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
RFC3	P40937, P40938

20. TP53 Regulates Metabolic Genes (R-HSA-5628897)

While the p53 tumor suppressor protein (TP53) is known to inhibit cell growth by inducing apoptosis, senescence and cell cycle arrest, recent studies have found that p53 is also able to influence cell metabolism to prevent tumor development. TP53 regulates transcription of many genes involved in the metabolism of carbohydrates, nucleotides and amino acids, protein synthesis and aerobic respiration.

TP53 stimulates transcription of TIGAR, a D-fructose 2,6-bisphosphatase. TIGAR activity decreases glycolytic rate and lowers ROS (reactive oxygen species) levels in cells (Bensaad et al. 2006). TP53 may also negatively regulate the rate of glycolysis by inhibiting the expression of glucose transporters GLUT1, GLUT3 and GLUT4 (Kondoh et al. 2005, Schwartzberg-Bar-Yoseph et al. 2004, Kawachi et al. 2008).

TP53 negatively regulates several key points in PI3K/AKT signaling and downstream mTOR signaling, decreasing the rate of protein synthesis and, hence, cellular growth. TP53 directly stimulates transcription of the tumor suppressor PTEN, which acts to inhibit PI3K-mediated activation of AKT (Stambolic et al. 2001). TP53 stimulates transcription of sestrin genes, SESN1, SESN2, and SESN3 (Velasco-Miguel et al. 1999, Budanov et al. 2002, Brynczka et al. 2007). One of sestrin functions may be to reduce and reactivate overoxidized peroxiredoxin PRDX1, thereby reducing ROS levels (Budanov et al. 2004, Papadia et al. 2008, Essler et al. 2009). Another function of sestrins is to bind the activated AMPK complex and protect it from AKT-mediated inactivation. By enhancing AMPK activity, sestrins negatively regulate mTOR signaling (Budanov and Karin 2008, Cam et al. 2014). The expression of DDIT4 (REDD1), another negative regulator of mTOR signaling, is directly stimulated by TP53 and TP63. DDIT4 prevents AKT-mediated inactivation of TSC1:TSC2 complex, thus inhibiting mTOR cascade (Cam et al. 2014, Ellisen et al. 2002, DeYoung et al. 2008). TP53 may also be involved, directly or indirectly, in regulation of expression of other participants of PI3K/AKT/mTOR signaling, such as PIK3CA (Singh et al. 2002), TSC2 and AMPKB (Feng et al. 2007).

TP53 regulates mitochondrial metabolism through several routes. TP53 stimulates transcription of SCO2 gene, which encodes a mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase assembly protein (Matoba et al. 2006). TP53 stimulates transcription of RRM2B gene, which encodes a subunit of the ribonucleotide reductase complex, responsible for the conversion of ribonucleotides to deoxyribonucleotides and essential for the maintenance of mitochondrial DNA content in the cell (Tanaka et al. 2000, Bourdon et al. 2007, Kulawiec et al. 2009). TP53 also transactivates mitochondrial transcription factor A (TFAM), a nuclear-encoded gene important for mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) transcription and maintenance (Park et al. 2009). Finally, TP53 stimulates transcription of the mitochondrial glutaminase GLS2, leading to increased mitochondrial respiration rate and reduced ROS levels (Hu et al. 2010).

The great majority of tumor cells generate energy through aerobic glycolysis, rather than the much more efficient aerobic mitochondrial respiration, and this metabolic change is known as the Warburg effect (Warburg 1956). Since the majority of tumor cells have impaired TP53 function, and TP53 regulates a number of genes involved in glycolysis and mitochondrial respiration, it is likely that TP53 inactivation plays an important role in the metabolic derangement of cancer cells such as the Warburg effect and the concomitant increased tumorigenicity (reviewed by Feng and Levine 2010). On the other hand, some mutations of TP53 in Li-Fraumeni syndrome may result in the retention of its wild-type metabolic activities while losing cell cycle and apoptosis functions (Wang et al. 2013). Consistent with such human data, some mutations of p53, unlike p53 null state, retain the ability to regulate energy metabolism while being inactive in regulating its classic gene targets involved in cell cycle, apoptosis and senescence. Retention of metabolic and antioxidant functions of p53 protects p53 mutant mice from early onset tumorigenesis (Li et al. 2012).

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Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2014-10-24	Created	Orlic-Milacic M
2014-12-23	Edited	Orlic-Milacic M
2014-12-23	Authored	Orlic-Milacic M
2014-12-30	Reviewed	Hwang PM, Kang JG, Wang PY

Date	Action	Author
2016-02-04	Reviewed	Zaccara S, Inga A
2023-05-21	Modified	Wright A

2 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 4 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
PTEN	P60484	RRAGD	Q9NQL2

Input	Ensembl Id
PTEN	ENSG00000171862, ENST00000371953

Interactors found in this pathway (1)

Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with	Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with
PTEN	P60484	P60484			

21. Regulation of TP53 Activity through Phosphorylation (R-HSA-6804756)

Phosphorylation of TP53 (p53) at the N-terminal serine residues S15 and S20 plays a critical role in protein stabilization as phosphorylation at these sites interferes with binding of the ubiquitin ligase MDM2 to TP53. Several different kinases can phosphorylate TP53 at S15 and S20. In response to double strand DNA breaks, S15 is phosphorylated by ATM (Banin et al. 1998, Canman et al. 1998, Khanna et al. 1998), and S20 by CHEK2 (Chehab et al. 1999, Chehab et al. 2000, Hirao et al. 2000). DNA damage or other types of genotoxic stress, such as stalled replication forks, can trigger ATR-mediated phosphorylation of TP53 at S15 (Lakin et al. 1999, Tibbetts et al. 1999) and CHEK1-mediated phosphorylation of TP53 at S20 (Shieh et al. 2000). In response to various types of cell stress, NUA1 (Hou et al. 2011), CDK5 (Zhang et al. 2002, Lee et al. 2007, Lee et al. 2008), AMPK (Jones et al. 2005) and TP53RK (Abe et al. 2001, Facchin et al. 2003) can phosphorylate TP53 at S15, while PLK3 (Xie, Wang et al. 2001, Xie, Wu et al. 2001) can phosphorylate TP53 at S20.

Phosphorylation of TP53 at serine residue S46 promotes transcription of TP53-regulated apoptotic genes rather than cell cycle arrest genes. Several kinases can phosphorylate S46 of TP53, including ATM-activated DYRK2, which, like TP53, is targeted for degradation by MDM2 (Taira et al. 2007, Taira et al. 2010). TP53 is also phosphorylated at S46 by HIPK2 in the presence of the TP53 transcriptional target TP53INP1 (D'Orazi et al. 2002, Hofmann et al. 2002, Tomasini et al. 2003). CDK5, in addition to phosphorylating TP53 at S15, also phosphorylates it at S33 and S46, which promotes neuronal cell death (Lee et al. 2007).

MAPKAPK5 (PRAK) phosphorylates TP53 at serine residue S37, promoting cell cycle arrest and cellular senescence in response to oncogenic RAS signaling (Sun et al. 2007).

NUAK1 phosphorylates TP53 at S15 and S392, and phosphorylation at S392 may contribute to TP53-mediated transcriptional activation of cell cycle arrest genes (Hou et al. 2011). S392 of TP53 is also phosphorylated by the complex of casein kinase II (CK2) bound to the FACT complex, enhancing transcriptional activity of TP53 in response to UV irradiation (Keller et al. 2001, Keller and Lu 2002).

The activity of TP53 is inhibited by phosphorylation at serine residue S315, which enhances MDM2 binding and degradation of TP53. S315 of TP53 is phosphorylated by Aurora kinase A (AURKA) (Katayama et al. 2004) and CDK2 (Luciani et al. 2000). Interaction with MDM2 and the consequent TP53 degradation is also increased by phosphorylation of TP53 threonine residue T55 by the transcription initiation factor complex TFIID (Li et al. 2004).

Aurora kinase B (AURKB) has been shown to phosphorylate TP53 at serine residue S269 and threonine residue T284, which is possibly facilitated by the binding of the NIR co-repressor. AURKB-mediated phosphorylation was reported to inhibit TP53 transcriptional activity through an unknown mechanism (Wu et al. 2011). A putative direct interaction between TP53 and AURKB has also been described and linked to TP53 phosphorylation and S183, T211 and S215 and TP53 degradation (Gully et al. 2012).

References

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Miki Y, Nihira K, Taira N, Yoshida K & Yamaguchi T (2007). DYRK2 is targeted to the nucleus and controls p53 via Ser46 phosphorylation in the apoptotic response to DNA damage. *Mol. Cell*, 25, 725-38. [↗](#)

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Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2015-10-14	Edited	Orlic-Milacic M
2015-10-14	Authored	Orlic-Milacic M
2015-10-14	Created	Orlic-Milacic M
2016-02-04	Reviewed	Zaccara S, Inga A
2023-05-30	Modified	Wright A

3 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 4 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
AURKA	O14965	RFC3	P40937, P40938	WRN	Q14191

22. Extension of Telomeres (R-HSA-180786)

Cellular compartments: nucleoplasm.

Telomerase acts as reverse transcriptase in the elongation of telomeres (Smogorzewska and de Lange 2004).

References

Smogorzewska A & de Lange T (2004). Regulation of telomerase by telomeric proteins. *Annu Rev Biochem*, 73, 177-208. [🔗](#)

Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2006-06-06	Created	Gillespie ME
2006-07-13	Reviewed	Price C
2009-06-03	Revised	D'Eustachio P
2020-02-12	Revised	Orlic-Milacic M
2020-04-29	Reviewed	Hayashi MT
2020-05-04	Edited	Orlic-Milacic M
2023-05-21	Modified	Wright A

3 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 4 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
FEN1	P39748	RFC3	P40937, P40938	WRN	Q14191

Interactors found in this pathway (4)

Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with	Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with
FEN1	P39748	Q14191	RFC3	P40938	P35249
WRN	Q14191	P39748	XIAP	P98170	P40937

23. G2/M DNA damage checkpoint (R-HSA-69473)

Throughout the cell cycle, the genome is constantly monitored for damage, resulting either from errors of replication, by-products of metabolism or through extrinsic sources such as ultra-violet or ionizing radiation. The different DNA damage checkpoints act to inhibit or maintain the inhibition of the relevant CDK that will control the next cell cycle transition. The G2 DNA damage checkpoint prevents mitotic entry solely through T14Y15 phosphorylation of Cdc2 (Cdk1). Failure of the G2 DNA damage checkpoint leads to catastrophic attempts to segregate unrepaired chromosomes.

References

Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2003-06-05	Created	Walworth N, O'Donnell M
2023-05-21	Modified	Wright A

2 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 3 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
RFC3	P40937, P40938	WRN	Q14191

Interactors found in this pathway (1)

Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with	Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with
PPP2R5D	Q14738	P30307			

24. Signaling by phosphorylated juxtamembrane, extracellular and kinase domain KIT mutants (R-HSA-9670439)

Diseases: cancer.

Activation of the PI3K/mTOR, RAS/MAPK and STAT signaling pathways has been observed downstream of activated extracellular, juxtamembrane and kinase domain mutants of KIT, although downstream signaling has not been studied in great detail in all cases. Activation of these pathways contributes to cellular proliferation, avoidance of apoptosis, and actin cytoskeletal organization (Dunesing et al, 2004; Bauer et al, 2007; Chi et al, 2010; Bosbach et al, 2017; reviewed in Lennartsson and Roonstrand, 2012; Corless et al, 2011).

References

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- Antonescu CR, Veach D, Ehlers I, Yozgat Y, Warpinski K, Besmer P, ... DeMatteo RP (2017). Direct engagement of the PI3K pathway by mutant KIT dominates oncogenic signaling in gastrointestinal stromal tumor. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.*, 114, E8448-E8457. [↗](#)

Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2019-12-09	Created	Rothfels K
2020-03-13	Reviewed	García-Valverde A, Pilco-Janeta D, Serrano C
2020-04-01	Authored	Rothfels K
2020-05-04	Edited	Rothfels K
2023-05-30	Modified	Wright A

1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 2 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
STAT1	P42224, P42224-1

25. Removal of the Flap Intermediate from the C-strand (R-HSA-174437)

Cellular compartments: nucleoplasm.

Two endonucleases, Dna2 and flap endonuclease 1 (FEN-1), are responsible for resolving the nascent flap structure (Tsurimoto and Stillman 1991). The Dna2 endonuclease/helicase in yeast is a monomer of approximately 172 kDa. Human FEN-1 is a single polypeptide of approximately 42 kDa. Replication Protein A regulates the switching of endonucleases during the removal of the displaced flap (Tsurimoto et al.1991).

References

Stillman B & Tsurimoto T (1991). Replication factors required for SV40 DNA replication in vitro. II. Switching of DNA polymerase alpha and delta during initiation of leading and lagging strand synthesis. *J Biol Chem*, 266, 1961-8. [🔗](#)

Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2006-02-18	Created	Gillespie ME
2006-03-10	Authored	Seidel J, Blackburn EH
2006-07-13	Reviewed	Price C
2009-06-03	Revised	D'Eustachio P
2019-12-02	Revised	Orlic-Milacic M
2020-04-29	Reviewed	Hayashi MT
2020-05-04	Edited	Orlic-Milacic M
2023-05-21	Modified	Wright A

2 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 2 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
FEN1	P39748

Input	UniProt Id
WRN	Q14191

Interactors found in this pathway (2)

Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with
FEN1	P39748	Q14191

Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with
WRN	Q14191	P39748

6. Identifiers found

Below is a list of the input identifiers that have been found or mapped to an equivalent element in Reactome, classified by resource.

29 of the submitted entities were found, mapping to 41 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
ANLN	Q9NQW6	AURKA	O14965	CENPF	P49454
CLTC	Q00610, Q00610-1	DHFR	P00374	DVL3	Q92997
ESCO2	Q56NI9	FEN1	P39748	FNIP1	Q8TF40
GTSE1	Q9NYZ3	HDAC6	Q9UBN7	KIF23	Q02241
KIF4A	O95239	MAPK8	P45983	NCAPG	Q9BPX3
PKMYT1	Q99640	PMS1	P54278	PPP2R5D	Q14738
PTEN	P60484	RFC3	P40937, P40938	RRAGD	Q9NQL2
RRM2	P31350	SPC24	Q8NBT2	STAT1	P42224, P42224-1
STMN1	P16949	TNF	P01375	UHRF1	Q96T88
WRN	Q14191	XIAP	P98170		

Input	Ensembl Id	Input	Ensembl Id	Input	Ensembl Id
CENPF	ENSG00000117724	DHFR	ENSG00000228716	PTEN	ENSG00000171862, ENST00000371953
RRM2	ENSG00000171848	STAT1	ENSG00000115415	STMN1	ENSG00000117632
TNF	ENSG00000232810				

Interactors (24)

Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with	Input	UniProt Id	Interacts with
AURKA	O14965	P53350, Q9ULW0	CLTC	Q00610	Q9NYZ3
DVL3	Q92997	Q96T60	ESCO2	Q56NI9	Q9NRD5
FEN1	P39748	P12004	GTSE1	Q9NYZ3	P53350
HDAC6	Q9UBN7	Q8IXJ6	KIF23	Q02241-2, Q02241	Q9H0H5
MAPK8	P45983	P05412	MKI67	P46013	Q9NS87
PKMYT1	Q99640	P20248, P61024, P06493, P14635, O95067	PMS1	P54277	P40692
PPP2R5D	Q14738	P30307	PTEN	P60484	P60484
RFC3	P40938	P35249	RRAGD	Q9NQL2	Q6IAA8, Q9UHA4
RRM2	P31350	Q9UM11	SHCBP1	Q9Z179	Q02241
STAT1	P42224	Q01094	STMN1	P16949	P46527
TNF	P01375	Q13546	UHRF1	Q96T88	P26358
WRN	Q14191	P39748	XIAP	P98170	P61024

Input	ChEBI Id	Interacts with	Input	ChEBI Id	Interacts with
RRAGD	Q9NQL2	15996			